

A Review on Recycle and Reuse of Plastic Waste to Manufacture Plastic Fly Ash Sand Brick and Compare It with Normal Clay Brick

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Abstract— The substantial increase in plastic production has led to a corresponding surge in plastic waste, prompting scientists and researchers to seek innovative and sustainable methods for recycling and reusing this waste to minimize its detrimental effects on the environment. Among various sectors, repurposing waste plastic in construction materials has garnered considerable attention due to its potential dual benefits. Not only does it reduce the volume of plastic waste ending up in landfills, but it also decreases reliance on mined construction materials, thereby mitigating the construction industry's environmental impact. This paper provides a comprehensive overview of advancements in incorporating plastic waste into construction materials. It examines how plastic waste can be used as a binder, aggregate, fine aggregate, modifier, or substitute for cement and sand in the production of bricks, tiles, concrete, and roads. Furthermore, it discusses the effects of adding plastic waste on properties such as strength, water absorption, and durability. The reviewed research studies are categorized based on whether they focus on utilizing plastic waste for bricks and tiles or in concrete for road construction.

Keywords— Plastic production, Plastic waste, Recycling methods, Sustainable reuse, Environmental impact, Construction materials

I. INTRODUCTION

Over time, the accumulation of plastic waste has become a pressing crisis due to ineffective disposal methods, resulting in widespread environmental contamination. Plastic waste has infiltrated various natural ecosystems, including water bodies, landfills, soil, and even the atmosphere, posing significant risks to biodiversity and human health. Despite its

durability, which is a notable characteristic of plastic, its inability to biodegrade fully means that it breaks down into smaller fragments over extended periods, perpetuating the pollution cycle. According to the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the global production of plastic exceeds 300 million tonnes annually, with only a fraction being recycled. UNEP's Executive Director, Inger Andersen, has highlighted the urgency of addressing this issue, warning that without intervention, landfills could accumulate over a billion metric tons of plastic by 2050. The COVID-19 pandemic has further exacerbated the problem, with the increased use and improper disposal of single-use plastic items such as personal protective equipment (PPE) contributing to what some describe as a "pandemic of plastic pollution." In recent years, the production of plastic has surged dramatically, resulting in a corresponding rise in plastic waste generation. However, a significant portion of this waste ends up in landfills or contaminates water bodies, exacerbating environmental degradation. Figure 1 illustrates the global trends in plastic production, while Figure 2 provides insight into the challenges associated with plastic waste management.

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Figure 1: Global Trends In Plastic Production

Due to their numerous beneficial qualities like durability, lightweight nature, resistance to water and corrosion, as well as being cost-effective and easy to transport, plastics have become essential materials in our lives. However, the excessive consumption and disposal of plastic have caused

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous research has focused on understanding the chemical properties of plastics to identify suitable types for manufacturing plastic bricks. Studies have examined the use of plastic waste in combination with other materials, such as laterite quarry waste, to develop alternative construction materials. Increasing the percentage of plastic content in significant environmental problems. To address this issue, maximizing recycling and reuse of plastic is crucial. Plastic waste can be repurposed in various sectors, including construction, fuel production, household items, textiles, and footwear.

The primary focus of this study is to thoroughly examine how plastic waste can be effectively utilized in construction materials. This paper explores different research methods that utilize plastic waste as a component in the production of bricks, tiles, and concrete, serving as a binder, aggregate, fine aggregate, modifier, or substitute for traditional materials like cement and sand.

In recent years, various reviews have explored the utilization of different waste materials in construction. Some studies focused on industrial waste like bottom ash and plastic waste as substitutes in concrete, while others examined the recycling techniques and effects of plastic waste on concrete properties. Additionally, there were reviews on the use of recycled materials in pavement concrete, properties of concrete with recycled plastic, and the impact of plastic waste on mortar and concrete composites. Furthermore, studies delved into the use of specific waste materials like PET and marble dust in construction, as well as the development of PET plastic bricks for specific applications. While these reviews provided valuable insights, there is still a need for a comprehensive analysis specifically focusing on the incorporation of plastic waste across various construction materials such as bricks, tiles, blocks, concrete, and road construction. This study aims to bridge this gap by providing a detailed review of various plastic waste materials and their suitability for different construction applications, along with an assessment of their impact on the strength and durability of the final products.

Figure 2: Types of plastic

III. CHALLENGES OF RECYCLING BRICKS

While recycling plastic waste offers numerous environmental advantages, there are several obstacles that hinder the process's effectiveness. One major issue is the environmental harm caused by recycling certain plastics, such as RIC 7 used in electronics, which emit harmful gases when melted. Additionally, plastics like polyvinyl chloride (PVC) and polystyrene (PS) release toxins and corrode when exposed to the environment.

Another challenge is the lack of clear guidelines for separating thermoplastic and thermoset plastics during packaging and recycling, making it difficult to recycle them effectively. Additionally, much of the plastic packaging is too toxic to be successfully recycled at the end of its life, leading to increased landfill waste.

Furthermore, inconsistent information about plastic recycling methods and applications poses a significant barrier to efficient recycling in the construction industry. Without standardized information, it's challenging to identify suitable recycling methods for different types of plastic waste.

CONCLUSION

In summary, with the increasing use of plastic in various products, recycling plastic offers a promising solution to combat pollution in our oceans and land. The construction industry can benefit greatly from advances in plastic recycling technology, especially in creating affordable and thermally efficient bricks for building structures like homes and schools.

Numerous studies have examined the qualities of plastic bricks, finding them to be lightweight, durable, and possessing strong compression compared to traditional bricks. Plastic bricks also excel in sound absorption and have low thermal conductivity. These features, combined with the cost-effectiveness of using recycled materials, highlight the potential of plastic waste in brick production.

Furthermore, using plastic waste in brick-making helps preserve valuable resources such as sand and clay, which are often depleted due to overuse. By adopting environmentally friendly and cost-effective methods, incorporating plastic waste into brick production emerges as both an economical and sustainable approach to tackle the adverse effects of improper plastic waste disposal.

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